

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NNAJI****FIRST NAME: ROBINSON****PROGRAM CODE: DPEI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 5 key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Tips on writing an academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8–11)
2. Structuring an academic essay(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10–12)
3. Rules of thumb for writing papers(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12–14)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34–39)
5. Writing style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44–57)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1)INTRODUCTION

The quest to improve my knowledge of epidemiology took me to apply to be allowed to study at Euclid University. I got admitted, completed the orientation, and resumed my studies. The first course I am taking is ACA-401D which has to do with essay writing, including the acceptable format of Euclid University. This course is a good step because I believe that doctorate degrees require many academic writings, and a new student needs to build his capacity in writing. Secondly, the way Euclid University's online activities are structured requires students to write academic papers ranging from response papers to main reports. I have read through the EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D and found that it teaches academic writing and other tactical knowledge, including a deeper understanding of using words that help in good academic writing (Elton 2010, 1).

In this response paper, I will discuss a few things I learned from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack and other readings I did. I will focus on writing academic articles, the basics, rules and steps, Plagiarism, and writing styles.

2) TIPS ON WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic essays are write-ups produced as part of the intellectual work of a student (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). It can range from this kind of paper (response paper) to a thesis, i.e., dissertations. It includes reports from field activities and scientific research. Abstracts, conference papers, and monographs are all academic writing. All academic papers share a standardized introduction, body, and conclusion format or, in a particular case, have an introduction, method, results, and discussion. Academic essays provide an answer to hypotheses aimed at knowledge addition. It also involves citing people's work while writing and referencing the authors we mentioned at the end (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D describes academic write-ups as "A prose register".

I will discuss these basics according to EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D under four sub-headings: starting an essay, researching the topic, organizing your idea, and the easy proper.

a) Starting an essay

One of the main lessons I learned in this paper is to avoid procrastination. Procrastination is never advisable in writing. To be a good writer, one should outgrow procrastination. Early start-up is vital in reporting, giving enough time to proofread and review. Apart from starting up early, analyzing the topic by defining and writing all we know is very helpful. If it is a hypothesis trying to provide the answer, following one's residual knowledge is advisable. Therefore, I now understand that analyzing the main questions, defining key terms, and finally establishing one's point of view is essential as this gives direction while writing. Finally, drafting an essay plan is the key to a good essay. According to Skybridge Consulting, "Failing to plan is planning to fail". If done correctly, an excellent, easy method will help answer research questions.

b) Researching the topic

Academic writing is mostly research papers. One needs to read widely on the proposed topic, search for what we know, brainstorm what we need to know, and what materials are available to support our writing. In-depth. According to the author, research on the proposed topic is essential to keep flow while writing. I also understood that I should filter relevant information while researching my case (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8–9). The best practice I learned is pinning documents, underlining relevant parts, and keeping photocopies. Creative thinking and mind mapping to broaden my view during writing are essential while using critical thinking to narrow the focus as I write.

c) Organizing my ideas

I learned that organizing my ideas involves writing the proper sequence of all your ideas in chronological order. The best practice is to design the table of content following our research and decide how best to answer the question answered logically (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). In doing this, I need to look through the notes I made while researching and provide plausible evidence for my answers.

d) Writing the essay

As I said before, I will have the mind to fight procrastination; the best practice is to come out with a first draft, putting our essay into an introduction, body, and conclusion. I also learned that leaving your draft paper for a day before we continue is good practice (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10). Multiple edits are also good practice in writing, while good formatting, citation, and referencing are all important.

3) STRUCTURING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Structuring an academic essay takes the format of an introduction, body, and conclusion. However, the body might be the method, results, and discussion in some scientific research.

Nonetheless, I learned what should be in each section. Starting with the introduction, I should use open with a short orientation of the topic using a funnel approach, i.e., from global to local I should also provide the objective and the main idea of the write-up.

In the body, I should provide ways I used to answer the research question and answers to the questions here. I should support my findings with plausible arguments with evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10). I also learned the importance of structuring the body of the paper into sections to deal with different questions.

Finally, in conclusion, I learned to write moving from specific to general (opposite of the introduction). It is also crucial that we restate the answer to the question we are answering and include a statement that is leading, providing future directions and or more research questions. It is also an excellent practice to be cautious to refrain from introducing new ideas in conclusion. We need to stay focused.

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR PAPER WRITING

In writing academic essays, I share the author's ideas on some basic rules. Stating the main focus of your paper at the beginning of the writing, possibly in the opening paragraphs, will help us to stay focused.

Talking of staying focused, this is very important as the author said we need to discuss the critical aspect of our thesis and follow through as we write (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13).

I also learned that while writing, I should, apart from being focused, I should refrain from using generalities, nor should I make my writing dull or clumsy. The best practice is to write thoughtfully and clearly while attributing your views to the person whose ideas you are addressing as you write (avoiding plagiarism). Critical reasoning and constructive criticism are also good practice in the author's views, and I concur with him as this will reduce objections.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is the use of someone's intellectual information without giving credit to him. I learned from the author that most of the time, plagiarism occurs when you use the word of a source without quotation marks and, secondly, if you take ideas from the start without footnoting the source. Plagiarism is wrong and unethical, according to the author (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). In writing, we need to avoid this by properly citing the author's source that has provided the information we are using. I also learned from the author that strict penalties await plagiarism in EUCLID. I also learned how to paraphrase to reduce plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36).

6) WRITING STYLE

Institutions develop writing styles to suit their needs. It leads to uniformity. At the same time, correct spelling and grammar are well-established and transparent when we say kind in writing. It is much more than punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary.

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to a certain element of writing style that needs to be consistent (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41).

The preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, dept of treating a subject, spelling (e.g., UK vs. US), readership consideration, and using abbreviations, terminologies, and symbols are all styles the author mentioned we consider while writing. Voice preference is also a style to consider, i.e., active vs. passive, use of headings, lists and trademarks, and many more.

I learned institutions and organizations can customize that style. I also learned that the Chicago Manual of Style is excellent, and EUCLID uses it.

7) CONCLUSION

The EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D course is very interactive and educative. I learned how to write academic essays, edit them and use proper referencing style. I also

learned the basic steps of writing while being exposed to some tips for writing. The author revealed Plagiarism to me, and I understood the use of style in writing.

The course is one someone always needs to revisit, as many write-ups are awaiting me in EUCLID.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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